

Guidelines for modeling and simulation of Ca-looping processes

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1 Calcium looping for post-combustion CO₂ capture applications

This part of the document is based on the carbonation-calcination loop (referred as Ca-looping, CaL, in the text) to separate CO₂ at high temperature of a flue gas stream coming from an existing coal-fired power plant or any other large CO₂ source. This process was first proposed by Shimizu et al. (1999), and proposes using CaO as a regenerable sorbent to remove CO₂ from the flue gas according to the following chemical reaction:

Although different process configurations have been proposed to implement this concept (Abanades et al., 2005), the general scheme of the CaL process is that depicted on Figure 1. Due to the huge flue gas flow to be put into contact with a solid stream, two interconnected circulating fluidized bed (CFB) reactors have been widely proposed to be used in this scheme due to the high gas throughput per unit area of these reactors.

Flue gas coming from an existing power plant is forced to enter into a carbonator reactor operating at 600-700°C and atmospheric pressure, where CO₂ reacts with CaO to be converted into CaCO₃. Solids from carbonator (mainly CaO and CaCO₃) are separated in a cyclone from the clean flue gas that is emitted to the atmosphere, and sent to a second reactor (calciner in Figure 1) where CaCO₃ is again decomposed into CaO that will be recirculated again to the carbonator reactor. Calciner needs to operate at a very high CO₂ partial pressure so that the gas produced can be easily purified and compressed to be sent to geological storage. According to the CaO-CaCO₃ equilibrium reaction and considering calciner working under atmospheric pressure, high CO₂ partial pressures in the calciner impose a temperature around 900°C to be under calcining conditions. Since CaCO₃ calcination is highly endothermic and solids from carbonator need to be heated up to calcination temperature, a large heat input need to be supplied to the calciner and therefore additional fuel has to be burnt in this reactor. Heat required in the CaL system depends mainly on process assumptions, like the type of fuel chosen to be burnt in the calciner or the fresh make-up flow and solid circulation considered to get a desired capture efficiency.

Combustion in the calciner is usually proposed to be carried out under oxy-combustion mode to avoid diluting the CO₂ gas stream arising from calciner with N₂ from air. The O₂ introduced in the calciner, coming from an Air Separation Unit, ASU, should be diluted by recycling part of the rich-CO₂ gas to avoid reaching excessive high local temperatures inside this reactor. In this way, CO₂ at the exit would be diluted mainly with steam coming from the hydrogen of the fuel burnt, which contributes to facilitate and make cheaper the purification process.

Figure 1 - Scheme of the CaL process focused on removing CO₂ from the flue gas of an existing power plant

Despite the fact that the calciner employs a great fraction of the total heat introduced in the CaL system (between 35-50 %) (Rodriguez et al., 2008), one of the main advantages of this capture technique is that this energy is recovered as gas streams at high temperature and as carbonation reaction heat from carbonator at 600-700°C. This high-quality heat recovered from the capture process is usually considered to be integrated into a power cycle to generate electricity, and therefore contributing to improve the efficiency of the plant with CO₂ capture. Furthermore, CaL system proposes using natural limestone as regenerable sorbent because of its low price and availability. The use of this CaO-based sorbent allows operating with flue gases with SO₂ content as it can be removed as CaSO₄, which would make unnecessary a desulphurisation unit in the power plant. As mentioned before, CaL relies on CFB technology and is proposed to operate under conditions similar to commercial CFB combustors, which allows CaL to take advantages from the knowledge and experience acquired about hydrodynamics and performance of these reactors (Diego et al., 2012). All these factors have made the CaL process being a rapidly developing technology with a great potential of reducing capture cost with lower efficiency penalties than other post-combustion technologies.

1.1 Large-scale carbonator reactor modelling

Different carbonator models have been proposed in the literature during years either to explain the experimental results obtained from experimental rigs, or to design higher scale plants and carry out predictions about their performance. A summary of the different carbonator models proposed in the literature is reported in Table 1. Different level of detail and complexity arise

from each of these carbonator models, but all of them have resulted to be useful tools in making preliminary calculations about carbonator performance under different operating conditions.

The first approach to the simulation of the carbonator in the CaL process came from Shimizu et al. (1999) that proposed a bubbling fluidized bed model to evaluate the required bed height of the carbonator to get an overall CO₂ removal efficiency of 90 %. The model proposed was based on that of Kunii and Levenspiel (1991) considering a two-region reactor: bubble and emulsion. This simple model was later adapted by Abanades et al. (2004) to the conditions of the experiments carried out in a fluidised bed carbonator, but including a full kinetic model for the carbonation reaction in two stages proposed by Bhatia and Perlmutter (1983). According to this kinetic model, carbonation reaction takes places in two stages at different reaction rate: a first regime of chemical reaction control where reaction occurs at the highest velocity, and a second period of product layer diffusion control due to the fact that the CaCO₃ layer thickness increases. The model of Abanades et al. (2004) showed that the most influencing parameter in the carbonator model was the fraction of particles reacting in the fast regime, especially in the later stages of the experiments, but remarked the need of a more detailed particle reaction model for these operating conditions, typical of the CaL process.

From that model onwards, carbonator models proposed in the literature considered the reactor as a circulating fluidised bed where two zones were distinguished: a bottom dense zone and a lean one located above. Except for the model of Alonso et al. (2009), which modelled the dense bed as an instantaneous and perfect mix of the solids with plug flow for the gas phase, the rest of the models proposed (Hawthorne et al., 2008; Lasheras et al., 2011; Romano, 2012) have been based on the core-annulus model of Kunii and Levenspiel (1997). Almost every of these models concluded that the most influencing parameter on the carbonator efficiency is the fraction of particles reacting in the fast regime, determined mainly by the fresh sorbent make-up flow introduced in the system and the solid circulation between reactors. Further level of detail in the fluid-dynamics has been considered in the reactor model developed by Romano (2012) that evaluated the CO₂ concentration profiles in the core and wall zone of the dense part, and the CO₂ profile in the lean zone. Moreover, this work included the effect of coal ashes and the deactivation of Ca-sorbent due to the presence of sulphur compounds.

1.1.1 Guidelines for future works

On the basis of the different carbonator reactor models reviewed, the following needs of research and consideration are highlighted in this field:

Accurate models on the CO₂ carrying capacity of the sorbent should be included to improve the reliability of the models and to better understand experimental results from pilot scale plants.

As a consequence of the sorbent recycling and make-up flow ratios used in a real CaL system, the CO₂ carrying capacity of the Ca-sorbent entering the carbonator will be different from that predicted because it depends on carbonation conditions (Arias et al., 2011; Lysikov et al., 2007; Sun et al., 2008), on the partial conversion achieved in the carbonator and calciner (Rodríguez et al., 2010) and on the possible reactivation mechanism carried out in the process (Arias et al., 2012; Martínez et al., 2011a). It is necessary an accurate model that considers the real age of the Ca particles in the system (N_{age}) according to their CO₂ carrying capacity, irrespective of their previous history of partial or complete cycles experimented in the CaL system. This N_{age} represents the number of equivalent carbonation/calcination cycles that the particles require to achieve a conversion equal to their carrying capacity, and depends on carbonation conditions, residence times in the reactors and also on certain regeneration techniques carried out. Carbonator models proposed should include accurate models on capture capacity that include this aspect.

Ca-based sorbent reactivity influence reactors design and, therefore, performance of the CaL process. Sorbent reactivity has been widely demonstrated to be influenced by the type of limestone chosen and its deactivation curve against carbonation-calcination cycles, and also by the sulphur content of the fuel used in the calciner.

Sulphur reacts not only with the CaO active for the carbonation reaction, but also can form CaSO₄ with the non-active CaO (Sun et al., 2005). Furthermore, the amount of Ca in the system with respect to the sulphur is of one order of magnitude higher than in conventional desulphurisation systems, and CaO conversion to CaSO₄ would be low enough for not considering a pore blocking mechanism. In this way, CaSO₄ formation would not entirely contribute to reduce the CaO prone to form CaCO₃. It is important to quantify this effect and determine the fraction of non-active CaO that reacts with sulphur to form CaSO₄ for not being excessively conservative when considering sulphur.

Furthermore, the use of a natural limestone with a large deactivation constant force to operate with a high CaCO₃ make-up flow or a high solid circulation rate to maintain a proper CO₂ capture capacity in the CaL system. In this way, it is important that the carbonator model proposed includes both deactivation mechanisms mentioned before to help and contribute to a more realistic design of the CaL system, and contribute to the scale-up of the technology.

Ashes from coal burnt in the calciner affect the amount of inerts circulating in the system and therefore, influence the heat required in the calciner to heat the solids up to calcination temperature. Moreover, the type of the fuel burnt in the calciner, determines the nature of the ashes and its facility to cause operating problems under certain

operating conditions. In this way, it is important to consider ashes in the simulation of CaL systems as thermal balances and operational issues are going to be affected.

Table 1 - Summary of the carbonator models published in the literature

PART (1/2)	Shimizu et al. (1999)	Abanades et al. (2004)	Hawthorne et al. (2008)	Alonso et al. (2009)
Particle conversion model/ equation	$\frac{dX}{dt} = C_{av} \cdot k \cdot (D - X)$ <p>Where: $C_{av} = \frac{(C_{in} - C_{out})}{\ln(C_{in}/C_{out})} \text{ (kmol/m}^3\text{)}$ D: maximum conversion (dX/dt=0), decreases with increasing N k=25 m³/kmol·s</p>	<p>Particle conversion model based on that proposed by Bhatia and Perlmutter (1983), including X_{b,N}:</p> $\frac{dX}{dt} = \begin{cases} k_x \cdot X_{b,N} \cdot (1 - X)^{2/3} \cdot (C_{CO_2} - C_{CO_2,eq}) & \text{if } X < X_{b,N} \\ 0 & \text{if } X > X_{b,N} \end{cases}$ <p>Where: $k_x = \frac{k_s \cdot S_0}{(1 - \varepsilon_0)}$ k_s=5.95·10⁻¹⁰ m⁴/mol·s S₀=40·10⁶ m²/m³ ε₀=0.5 (particle porosity) X_{b,N}: maximum carbonation conversion at the end of the fast reaction stage for a cycle N C_{CO₂}, C_{eq}: CO₂ concentration in the bulk phase and in the equilibrium, respectively</p>	<p>Particle conversion model based on that suggested by Bhatia and Perlmutter (1983), but modified including the maximum carrying capacity of the sorbent, X_{max}:</p> $\frac{dX}{dt} = \frac{k_s \cdot S_0}{(1 - \varepsilon_0)} \cdot (X_{max} - X)^{2/3} \cdot (C_{CO_2} - C_{CO_2,eq})$ <p>Where: k_s=5.95·10⁻¹⁰ m⁴/mol·s S₀=40·10⁶ m²/m³ ε₀=0.5 (particle porosity) C_{CO₂}, C_{eq}: CO₂ concentration in the bulk phase and in the equilibrium, respectively</p>	<p>Average reaction rate of the active material, r_{ave}, based on that proposed by Abanades et al. (2004) removing the term (1-X)^{2/3}:</p> $r_{ave} = \begin{cases} k_s \cdot S_{ave} \cdot (C_{CO_2} - C_{eq}) & \text{if } \tau < t^* \\ 0 & \text{if } \tau > t^* \end{cases}$ <p>Where: k_s=4·10⁻¹⁰ m⁴/mol·s $S_{ave} = \frac{X_{ave} \cdot \rho_{CaO} / PM_{CaO}}{\varepsilon_{max} \cdot \rho_{CaCO_3} / PM_{CaCO_3}}$ Being e_{max} the maximum thickness of the CaCO₃ layer formed on the pore wall (50 nm) C_{CO₂}, C_{eq}: CO₂ concentration in the bulk phase and in the equilibrium, respectively t*: time that marks the end of the fast reaction period</p>
Sorbent capacity decay law	<p>Although it is observed a sorbent capacity decay, it is not considered and it is taken D<0.3</p>	$X_{b,N} = f_m^N \cdot (1 - f_w) + f_w$ <p>(Abanades and Alvarez, 2003) With f_m and f_w depending on the limestone tested</p>	<p>Decay sorbent capacity law base on that proposed by Abanades (2002) but depending on the CaCO₃ content X_{carb} achieved:</p> $X_{max} = \sum_{N=1}^{N=\infty} \frac{F_0}{F_R} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{F_0}{F_R}\right)^{(N-1)} \cdot X_{N,pc}$ <p>Being X_{N,pc} the maximum conversion achievable in cycle N due to partial carbonation up to having a content X_{carb}</p>	<p>Maximum conversion in each cycle, X_N:</p> $X_N = \frac{1}{(1-X_r)^{N+1} + N \cdot k} + X_r$ <p>(Grasa and Abanades, 2006)</p>
Hydrodynamic regime of the reactor	BFB	BFB (Intermediate regime between fast and slow bubbles)	CFB	CFB
Hydrodynamic model	Two-regions: bubble and emulsion model of Kunii and Levenspiel (1991)	Two-regions: bubble and emulsion model of Kunii and Levenspiel (1991)	<p>Three regions each with its hydrodynamic and reaction model: Lower region of the CFB <i>Region I.</i> Dense bed: bubble and emulsion model of Kunii and Levenspiel (1991) Upper region of the CFB (riser): core-annulus flow structure modeled by Pugsley and Berruti (1996), that divide the riser into two regions: <i>Region II.</i> Acceleration region (developing upward velocity and voidage) <i>Region III.</i> Fully-developed flow region (flow characteristics invariant with height)</p>	Instantaneous and perfect mixing of the solids (CSTR) and plug flow (PF) for the gas phase

Particle distribution	Uniform (0.42-0.59 mm)	Average particle sizes around 1 mm	Uniform (500 μm)	Kinetic parameters chosen correspond to highly cycled particles (maintain a nearly constant size)
Criteria for reactor dimensioning	Cross-sectional area of the carbonator is an input variable to the model (973 m ² , determined by flow rate of gas and superficial gas velocity, 1.35 m/s) whereas reactor height is an objective of the reactor model (2.4 m, determined by heat transfer).	Reactor dimensions (height and cross-sectional area) are input variables to the model, as well as the superficial gas velocity and the solid inventory. Moreover, the fraction of active CaO reacting in the fast reaction regime (f_a) has to be provided to the model.	Reactor dimensions (height and cross-sectional area) are input variables to the model, as well as the gas inlet velocity and the solid inventory. Reactor dimensions are 12 m of height and 0.07 m of diameter. The fraction of free active CaO, f_a , have to be also introduced to the model and will result into a carbonation rate constant to be introduced into the model.	Results have been evaluated per m ² of cross-sectional area of carbonator and using a dimensionless variable for height. Solid inventory is given in kg/MW and to give the results per m ² of cross-sectional area, it is considered that typical heat duty in CFB combustors is 5 MW/m ² . Flue gas entering the carbonator contains 0.1 kg CO ₂ /s with 0.15 of volumetric fraction of CO ₂ .
Effect of coal ash included	No	No	No directly, but an average solid density of 1800 kg/m ³ has been considered	No
Effect of sulfur included	No (considered total removal of S in the CFB combustor prior to carbonator)	No (since Ca/S ratios in this system will be >20, effective capture of SO ₂ might be achieved without affecting carbonation)	No	No directly, although it has been considered the need of a solid purge to remove ashes and CaSO ₄ .
Governing parameters	Heat removal from the carbonator is the limiting factor as it determines the reactor height needed, and therefore, the CO ₂ captured.	f_a has a great influence in the sensitivity of the model, concretely when having low values of f_a (or what it is the same, to the later stages in the carbonation cycles during experiments). In these cases, the sensitivity of the model to the reactivity of the sorbent is even more pronounced.	The most important parameter affecting carbonator performance is the active fraction f_a (model input), especially for values below 0.3. Other parameters having significant influence are the carbonator temperature (especially in the riser region) and the solid inventory.	The fraction of active particles in the bed (f_a) is the most important variable in the CO ₂ concentration profile in the carbonator, and therefore in the CO ₂ capture efficiency. The variables determining f_a are: solid inventory, F_R/F_{CO_2} and F_0/F_{CO_2} .
Results	Bed height determined by heat removal was found to be enough for achieving more than 83 % of CO ₂ capture, that is 90 % of overall CO ₂ recovery.	CO ₂ concentration profiles in the reactor are insensitive to values of f_a higher than 0.1. For low values of f_a (typical of continuous operation of the CaL), general bed characteristics (such as superficial gas velocity, bed temperature, bed height, bubble behavior,...) strongly affects the CO ₂ capture efficiency.	More than 70 % of CO ₂ capture is achieved for a range of reasonable conditions: 600-650°C, $f_a > 0.075$, 4-5 kg/s of solid inventory) Most of the CO ₂ capture is observed to be occurring in the first 2 m (1.2 m of dense region) with a significant fraction occurring in the acceleration region due to the better gas-solid contact than in the dense region.	CO ₂ capture efficiencies > 80 % are feasible with solid inventories higher than 200 kg/MW and solid circulation rates higher than 3 kg/m ² ·s ($F_{Ca}/F_{CO_2} \sim 5$) To increase capture efficiency up to 90 %, maintaining solid inventory, solid circulation rate should be increased up to 6 kg/m ² ·s

PART (2/2)	Lasheras et al. (2011)	Romano (2012)
Particle conversion model/ equation	<p>Particle conversion model is that suggested by Abanades et al. (2004):</p> $\frac{dX}{dt} = k_s \cdot \frac{X_{b,N} \cdot S_0 \cdot \rho_{CaO}}{M_{CaO}} \cdot (1 - X)^{2/3} \cdot (C_{CO_2} - C_{CO_2,eq})$ <p>$k_s = 5.95 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ m}^4/\text{mol} \cdot \text{s}$ $S_0 = 40 \cdot 10^6 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^3$ $X_{b,N}$: active fraction of CaO entering the carbonator given by Abanades et al. (2005) as:</p>	<p>Particle conversion model based on the carbonation rate suggested by Grasa et al. (2008), similar to that proposed by Bhatia and Perlmutter (1983):</p> $\frac{dX}{dt} = k_s \cdot S_N \cdot (1 - X)^{2/3} \cdot (C_{CO_2} - C_{CO_2,eq})$ <p>This reaction rate is valid for $t < t_{lim}$, which corresponds to the time required by the sorbent particle to reach complete conversion. For $t > t_{lim}$, reaction rate becomes zero.</p>

	$X_{b,N} = \frac{f_m \cdot (1 - f_w) \cdot F_0}{F_0 + F_R \cdot (1 - f_m)} + f_w$ <p>ρ_{CaO} and M_{CaO} are the CaO density and CaO molar weight</p>	$t_{lim} = \frac{3 \cdot [1 - (1 - X_{max,N})^{1/3}]}{k_r \cdot (C_{CO_2} - C_{CO_2,eq})}$ <p>$k_r=6.05 \cdot 10^{-10}$ (m⁴/mol·s) C_{CO_2}, C_{eq}: CO₂ concentration in the bulk phase and in the equilibrium, respectively S_N: specific surface area available in a particle having been cycled N times ($V_{M_{CaCO_3}}=36.9 \cdot 10^{-6}$ m³/mol) $S_N = \frac{V_{M_{CaCO_3}} \cdot X_{max,N}}{M_{CaO} \cdot 50 \cdot 10^{-9}} \cdot \rho_{CaO}$</p>
Sorbent capacity decay law	$X_{b,N} = f_m^N \cdot (1 - f_w) + f_w$ <p>(Abanades and Alvarez, 2003)</p>	$X_{max,N} = \frac{1}{1/(1 - X_r) + k \cdot N} + X_r$ <p>With $k=0.52$ and $X_r=0.075$ (without sulfur deactivation) (Grasa and Abanades, 2006)</p>
Hydrodynamic regime of the reactor	CFB	CFB
Hydrodynamic model	Core-annulus model with an upper lean and a lower dense region based on an approach for CFB of Kunii and Levenspiel (1997)	Core-annulus model with an upper lean and a lower dense region proposed by (Kunii and Levenspiel, 1997, 2000)
Particle distribution	Constant particle diameter of d_p (value not specified)	Uniform particle diameter (justified since d_p does not affect kinetics and absorption capacity, Grasa and Abanades (2006))
Criteria for reactor dimensioning	Flue gas coming from a 1052 MW _e reference plant has to be divided by half and therefore, assuming an 80% of capture efficiency and a superficial velocity of 6 m/s, 194 m ² of cross-sectional area of the carbonator is needed. It has been set a reactor height of 30 m.	H_i (overall height of the riser) is an input variable to the model, as well as u_0 (mean superficial velocity in the riser) and solid inventory. A (riser cross-section) will be calculated from the mean volumetric flow between reactor inlet and outlet (result from solving the model) and u_0 .
Effect of coal ash included	Yes, to account for the solid density in the bed and the total solid inventory	Yes, ashes are considered in solid inventory and molar mass of solids in the system (that will affect to the solid residence time), and in the volume ratio ξ between active solids and total solids.
Effect of sulfur included	Not considered in the sorbent decay law (high ratio Ca/S), but a 99% of conversion of the SO ₂ in the flue gas is achieved	Yes, considered in the sorbent decay law through the parameters k and X_r for different sulfation levels.
Governing parameters	Performance strongly depends on the ratio F_R/F_{CO_2} and the solid inventory (through the pressure drop), and to a lesser extent of the ratio F_0/F_{CO_2}	Carbonator capture efficiency is strongly linked to the following input variables: ratios F_0/F_{CO_2} and F_R/F_{CO_2} , solid inventory and sulfur and ash content of the coal burnt. Furthermore, model parameters related to sorbent performance (k and X_r) have also a strong influence on capture efficiency.
Results	80 % of CO ₂ captured (an objective fixed in the model), 14 kPa of pressure drop and 55 tonnes/h of make-up flow, maximize net plant efficiency.	The model is used for evaluating the effect of different parameters in the carbonator performance, and it is expected that the model will be used to optimize the operating parameters of the CaL system that minimizes the cost of CO ₂ avoided

1.2 Power plant simulations including CaL for CO₂ capture

Integration between a power plant and the CaL system relies on introducing the flue gas from the boiler (after cooling) into the carbonator of the capture system. In case of retrofitting applications, usually considered in the literature, no modifications in the existing power plant are expected in this way, but power production (and then electric efficiency) would decrease because of the additional fuel consumed in the calciner and the energy consumption of the ASU and the CO₂ compression train required in the CaL system. However, one of the main advantages of the CaL system as a post-combustion CO₂ capture mechanism is that the chemical energy introduced in the system for sorbent regeneration with the fuel burned in the calciner is recovered as gas streams at high temperature, and as carbonation heat at 600-700°C. This energy is usually proposed to be integrated in a power cycle to generate extra electricity which improves the efficiency of the whole plant.

There are two ways proposed to use the energy recovered from the CaL system. The first one makes use of this energy in the existing power plant to produce extra steam and to reduce coal consumption in the boiler (Romeo et al., 2010; Yongping et al., 2010). In this option, a tight thermal integration between the existing power plant and the capture process is required, which limits its operational flexibility, and makes necessary new designs for the steam cycle. This integration is more appropriate for new construction power plants with CO₂ capture, and therefore, represents an option in a longer term. The second integration deals with the integration of the energy released from the CaL system into a new steam cycle decoupled to the existing power plant, without involving modifications on its performance (Figure 2). In this option, the CaL system is thermally integrated with a new efficient steam cycle and both systems would act as an oxy-fired plant, with no integration between the existing power plant and the CO₂ capture plant but for the flue gas exiting the boiler that enters into the carbonator. This retrofit option is the most-ready-to-use option in the short to medium term as it can take advantage of existing power plants to fulfil CO₂ constraints without major modifications.

Figure 2 - General layout for the existing power plant integrated with the CaL system

A summary of the different research works and results published on the literature are gathered in Table 2. Most of the works reviewed consider the integration of the CaL system into a coal-fired power plant coupled with a high-efficiency supercritical steam cycle (Abanades et al., 2005; Epple and Ströhle, 2008; Hawthorne et al., 2009; Martínez et al., 2011b; Romano, 2009; Romeo et al., 2008; Romeo et al., 2009; Shimizu et al., 1999; Ströhle et al., 2009a; Ströhle et al., 2009b), according to the thermal integration depicted in Figure 2. Yongping et al. (2010) analyses several methods for the utilisation of the heat recovered from the CaL system, and proposes modifications and some developments in the boiler and steam turbine of the existing plant. Low electric efficiencies have been reported in this work for all the schemes proposed because heat recovered from the CaL system has not been fully integrated into the plant. However, it concludes that the only option likely to be developed in a near future is to use the heat recovered from the CaL system to drive a new steam cycle, as it does not affect the operation of the existing plant.

A common feature of the works reviewed is estimating an electric efficiency of the whole process that results from coupling a CaL system into an existing coal-fired power plant, and considering usually a supercritical steam cycle that takes advantage of the heat fluxes available in the capture plant. Conventionally, the capture system has been assumed to be working under a fixed and reasonable operating conditions in both reactors: carbonator at 600-650°C with CO₂ capture efficiency of 90 %, and calciner at 900-950°C considering full calcination of the CaCO₃ coming from carbonator, usually without CO₂ recycle in the calciner. Romeo et al. (2009) and Martínez et al. (2011b) carried out a sensitivity analysis to assess system performance under different operating conditions of the CaL system, and determine the optimum fresh sorbent make-up flow and solid circulation for the CaL from an economical (Romeo et al., 2009) or an efficiency point of view (Martínez et al., 2011b). Both works conclude that working with low purge percentages and high solid circulation between reactors lead to the highest electric efficiencies and the lowest costs per tCO₂ captured. Romeo et al. (2009) even quantify that the maximum solid purge should be 5 % to avoid capture costs above 20 €/tCO₂ captured.

Quantitatively, when comparing with a reference plant without capture, a broad range of electric efficiencies have been reported. Lower efficiency penalties of the order of 3 percentage points have been assessed by Epple and Ströhle (2008), Ströhle et al. (2009a) and Ströhle et al. (2009b) that do not include CO₂ compression or fan consumption in the calciner. Abanades et al. (2005) analysed the efficiency obtained for different configuration schemes of the CaL, and assessed a penalty of 5.75 percentage points with respect to a reference plant of 46 % of electric generation efficiency, being 2.85 and 3.17 percentage points attributed to the CO₂ compressor and the ASU, respectively. In the rest of the reviewed works, efficiency penalties are typically between

6.5 and 8.5 percentage points with respect to the reference plant. Reasons for these differences are the electric efficiency for the reference plant assumed, the different qualities of the thermal integration proposed, the fact that in some cases no thermal integration has been carried out and a reasonable electric efficiency has been applied to the total heat recovered from the CaL, or the different power consumptions assumed for the auxiliaries, compressors and fans with respect to other works.

1.2.1 Guidelines for future works

From the papers reviewed here, it has been noticed that there is a lack of benchmark guidelines for comparison among the different published works. Main parameters affecting not only the CaL system (like the ASU, CO₂ compressor, fans, ...) but also those of the reference power plant should be collected and reported as a basis for comparison of the different works. The main objective of these guidelines would be to make results more consistent and reliable, and also easy to be compared with other technologies. For instance, reference to the European Benchmarking Task Force (EBTF) (Franco et al., 2011) can be made, at least for the fundamental techno-economic assumptions.

In addition, the following suggestions can be made for future modelling and simulation works:

The power consumption of auxiliary units should be properly taken into account. In particular, the consumption of the fan needed to offset the flue gas pressure losses in the carbonator should be included, since it may provide a relevant contribution to the auxiliary electric consumption. For a reliable estimation of this consumption, it is important to consider the presence of inactive solids (inactive sorbent, ash from coal and CaSO₄) as part of the carbonator inventory and to use a carbonator model to estimate the link between the fundamental CaL process parameters (carbonator inventory, sorbent make-up and sorbent recycle rate) and CO₂ capture efficiency.

Improvements on the calculation methodology of the oxy-fuel combustion side should be made with respect to the existing literature, where it is often treated in a simplified way. For example, flue gas recycle and CO₂ compression and purification unit should be considered in future works.

Assessments on the effects of different kinetics and stability of the sorbent on the overall plant performance are lacking in the current literature. As cited in the former section, considering the CO₂ absorption capacity of the sorbent through the actual age of the particles cycled in the system allows a better assessment of the whole performance, and makes the results obtained more reliable. Longer carbonation times (Arias et al., 2011; Lysikov et al., 2007; Sun et al., 2008) or certain reactivation processes with steam (Martínez et al., 2011) or CO₂ (Arias et al., 2012) impact sorbent

reactivity, and have been gaining further attention. Performance of the whole plant including some of these reactivation methods should be assessed.

Table 2 - Summary of the assumptions and results obtained from process simulation on CaL process integrated with coal-fired power plants

PART (1/2)	Ref1: Authors (year)	Shimizu et al. (1999)	Abanades et al. (2005)	Romeo et al. (2008)	Romeo et al. (2009)	
Fuel (existing plant and calciner)	Composition and LHV-HHV	Coal burnt in the existing plant is the same burnt in the calciner: Bituminous coal, HHV=33.2 MJ/kg-daf (LHV=23.61 MJ/kg) C: 69.2 % (wt) H: 4 % (wt) O: 9.3 % (wt) Ash: 17.5 % (wt) Moisture: 9.8 % (wt)	Coal burnt in the combustor and in the calciner is the same: LHV=25 MJ/kg C: 65.0 % (wt) H: 3.0 % (wt) O: 8.0 % (wt) S: 0.0 % (wt) Ash: 16.0 % (wt) Moisture: 8.0 % (wt)	In the <u>existing plant</u> , a low-rank high-sulphur lignite is used: LHV=15.854 MJ/kg C: 42.2 % (wt) H: 2.7 % (wt) O: 7.0 % (wt) N: 0.7 % (wt) S: 4.8 % (wt) Ash: 23.5 % (wt) Moisture: 19.1 % (wt) In the <u>calciner</u> , a low-sulphur high rank coal is used: LHV= 25.2 MJ/kg C: 66.9 % (wt) H: 3.7 % (wt) O: 6.5 % (wt) N: 1.6 % (wt) S: 0.7 % (wt) Ash: 13.9 % (wt) Moisture: 6.8 % (wt)	In the existing plant, a high-rank coal is burnt with air (66 % (wt.) of C; 8 % (wt.) of H ₂ O; 13 % (wt.) of ashes, and LHV=25.3 MJ/kg). Concerning the coal burnt in the calciner, the influence of the coal burnt in the calciner is analysed. Coals with different ash and sulphur contents are considered.	
Type of plant	Greenfield/retrofit	Retrofit of an existing air-blown coal-fired supercritical power plant coupled with a new supercritical steam cycle which energy is provided by CaL system	Retrofit of an existing reference power plant with CaL system coupled with a new steam cycle	Retrofit an existing supercritical power plant with a new supercritical steam cycle coupled with a CaL system	Retrofit of an existing power plant with a CaL system coupled with a new supercritical steam cycle	
Carbonator	Operating temperature, °C F ₀ /F _{CO2} F _{CaO} /F _{CO2} W _s , kg/MW or kg/m ² Ca conversion*, % CO ₂ capture efficiency, % Gas pressure drop, kPa Model used Others?	600°C No make-up flow F _{CaO} /F _{CO2} of 8.3 ~ 685 kg/m ² CaO conversion: 10 %	650°C F ₀ /F _{CO2} =0.10 F _{CaO} /F _{CO2} =3 - 25.1 % (=maximum average conversion, X _{ave}) 75.3 % of CO ₂ captured	650°C F ₀ /F _{CO2} =0.25 (F ₀ /F _{Ca} =0.05) F _{CaO} /F _{CO2} = 5 - 17 % of CaO conversion 85 % of CO ₂ captured	650°C F ₀ /F _R =0.02 F _{CaO} /F _{CO2} =4 - 22.1 % (=X _{ave}) 96 % of CO ₂ captured	F ₀ /F _R =0.015 F _{CaO} /F _{CO2} =5 - 22.4 % (=X _{ave})
		~ 83 % (it is fixed by the author)	75.3 % of CO ₂ captured	85 % of CO ₂ captured	96 % of CO ₂ captured	
		Not mentioned	-	-	Not specified	
		BFB for intermediate size particle of Kunii and Levenspiel	There is no a reactor model implemented (CaO conversions are considered to be equal to X _{ave})	There is no a reactor model implemented	There is no a reactor model implemented	
		Ca(OH) ₂ is not formed CaSO ₄ is not formed		CaSO ₄ is considered	CaSO ₄ formed	
Calciner	Operating temperature, °C Calcination efficiency, %	950°C 100 % of CaCO ₃ calcined	950°C 100 % of CaCO ₃ calcined	875°C -	930°C 100 % of CaCO ₃ calcined	

	O ₂ content in oxidant stream, % CO ₂ recycle, % O ₂ content in calciner flue gas, %	- - -	100 % O ₂ fed into the calciner 0 % of rich-CO ₂ recirculated -	100 % O ₂ (there is no CO ₂ recirculation) 0 % of rich-CO ₂ recirculated Not mentioned	30 % O ₂ 17-21 % of rich-CO ₂ recirculated Not mentioned
Steam cycle	SH/RH pressure, bar SH/RH temperature, °C BFW temperature, °C Condensing pressure, bar Turbine isentropic efficiency HP/IP/LP, % Electric-mechanical efficiency, %	172.21 bar/30.39 bar 566°C/538°C ~ 250-300°C - - 100 %		280 bar/40 bar 600°C/600°C 285°C 0.045 bar -	290 bar/48.5 bar 600°C/620°C - 0.045 bar 89 % for HP turbine and 91 % for IP and LP turbines -
Air separation unit	Consumption for O ₂ production, kWh/t _{O2} O ₂ purity, % vol.	25.9 MJ _e /kmol (~225 kW _e h/t _{O2}) 97.5 % O ₂ purity		220 kWh/ton O ₂ (Metz et al., 2005) 95 % O ₂	220 kWh/ton O ₂ (Metz et al., 2005) 95 % O ₂
CO ₂ compression and purification	Final CO ₂ pressure, bar Final CO ₂ purity, % Number of IC compressors Compressors isentropic efficiency, % Electric-mechanical efficiency, % Overall specific consumption, kJ/kgCO ₂	- > 95% (dry basis) - - - 24.5 MJ _e /kmol-CO ₂ (~ 155 kWh/t _{CO2})	100 bar	110 bar Not specified - - -	120 bar (80°C) Not specified 4 turbo compressors 80 % isentropic efficiency -
Other auxiliaries	Fans isentropic efficiency, % Fans electric-mechanical efficiency, % Coal handling and milling, kJ/kg coal Limestone handling and milling, kJ/kg Others?			- - - -	
Results	Gross power, MW _e ASU consumption, MW _e CO ₂ compression consumption, MW _e Fans consumptions, MW _e Net power, MW _e Net efficiency, % (Net output/heat of coal)	1000 MW _e (465 MW _e CaL) 69 MW _e 114 MW _e - 817 MW _e 33.4 % (HHV)// 34.9 % (LHV)	46 MW _e 3.2 MW _e 2.6 MW _e - 40.3 MW _e 40.25 % (LHV)	736 MW _e (308.5 MW _e CaL) 46.6 MW _e 52.8 MW _e (fans, solid and gas circulation and CO ₂ compr.) 15.4 MW _e (power plant auxil.) 621.2 MW _e (193.7 MW _e CaL) 37.04 % (1677.24 MW_{th} coal, LHV)	875.3 MW _e 856.8 MW _e 61.9 MW _e 59.6 MW _e CO ₂ compression turbine is driven by steam extraction from the IP turbine 24.7 MW _e 24.7 MW _e 788.7 MW _e 772.6 MW _e 35.62 % (LHV) coal of exist. plant 35.50 % (LHV) coal of exist. plant

	CO ₂ capture ratio, % Credits for integration with cement industry** Specific CO ₂ emission, g/kWh	90.4 % No credits as solid purge has not been considered 77.6 g CO ₂ /kWh gross //95.0 g CO ₂ /kWh net	90 % 1.10 points of increase (41.3 % (LHV) net effic.) 141.1 g CO ₂ /kWh net	88.7 % 2.92 points of increase (39.96 % of net efficiency) 122 g CO ₂ /kWh net	0.67 points (36.30 %) 21.9 g CO ₂ /kWh net	0.70 points (36.20 %) Not specified
Comparison with reference plant w/o CO ₂ capture***	Efficiency penalty, % points	7.22 points (40.7 % (HHV) reference plant) // 7.54 points (42.4 % (LHV) reference)	5.75 points of energy penalty (46 % (LHV) reference plant)	7.89 points of energy penalty without integration with cement industry (44.9 % reference plant) 83.6 % (781 g CO ₂ /kWh net existing plant)	6.76 points of penalty (42.4 % reference)	6.83 points of penalty (42.3 % reference)
	Reduced specific emission, %	89.1 % (872.3 g CO ₂ /kWh net existing plant)	81.1 % (746.1 g CO ₂ /kWh net existing plant)		97.6 % (905.1 g CO ₂ /kWh net existing plant)	Not information available
Notes *Ca conversion referred to the unsulfated sorbent and defined as: $\frac{x_{CaO}}{x_{CaO} + x_{CaCO_3}}$ **Credits for cement industry have been evaluated as: $Credits = \left(\frac{Net\ power}{H_{coal,RP} + H_{coal,calciner} - H_{calc,F0} - Net\ efficiency} \right) \cdot 100$ H _{calc,F0} : Heat required to calcine the Ca contained in F ₀ (H _{calc} =182.9 MW/kmol) ***Reference plant has been considered as the existing one and a new one with the same fuel input as the calciner			Base case of 100 MW _{th} introduced as coal in the plant (sum of calciner and boiler) Electricity generation efficiency is 46 % for reference plant and heat from CaL	The net efficiency of the existing and the new steam cycle are the same and equal to 44.4 %	Ratios F ₀ /F _R and F _{CaO} /F _{CO₂} are those that minimize the avoided CO ₂ cost under two scenarios: solid purge at carbonator (column left) and purge at calciner (column right). Apart from the heat recovered from the CaL system, <u>heat from the CO₂ compression train has been also integrated into the new supercritical steam cycle</u> , while a steam extraction of the turbine is used for driving the CO ₂ turbo compressor <u>45 % of efficiency of an SC steam cycle is considered</u>	

PART (2/2)	Ref1: Authors (year)	Romano (2009)	Epple and Ströhle (2008), Ströhle et al. (2009a), Ströhle et al. (2009b), Lasheras et al. (2011)	Hawthorne et al. (2009)	Yongping et al. (2010)	Martínez et al. (2011b)
Fuel (existing plant and calciner)	Composition and LHV-HHV	Low sulphur South African coal is used in the plant: LHV= 24.62 MJ/kg C: 64.4 % (wt) H: 4.0 % (wt) O: 7.4 % (wt) N: 1.5 % (wt) S: 0.9 % (wt)	Bituminous coal which ultimate or proximate analysis is not specified	Not specified neither its analysis nor its heating value although	Coals used have been taken from Romeo et al. (2008)	In the <u>existing plant</u> , a low-rank high-sulphur lignite is used: LHV=17.02 MJ/kg C: 45.2 % (wt) H: 3.0 % (wt) O: 7.2 % (wt) N: 0.8 % (wt) S: 4.1 % (wt)

		Ash: 12.7 %(wt) Moisture: 9.4 %(wt)				Ash: 22.4 %(wt) Moisture: 17.3 %(wt) In the <u>calciner</u> , a low-sulphur high rank coal is used: LHV= 25.3 MJ/kg C: 66.3 %(wt) H: 3.6 %(wt) O: 7.0 %(wt) N: 1.6 %(wt) S: 0.6 %(wt) Ash: 14.2 %(wt) Moisture: 6.7 %(wt)
Type of plant	Greenfield/retrofit	A plant of new construction where a fraction of coal is burnt with air in a boiler and the remaining fraction is burnt in oxy-fuel mode in the calciner. The energy recovered from both boilers generates an ultra-supercritical steam that feeds a steam turbine	Retrofit of an existing coal-fired power plant with a CaL system coupled with a new supercritical steam cycle	Retrofit of an existing coal-fired power plant with a CaL system coupled with a new supercritical steam cycle	Introducing a CaL system into an existing supercritical power plant and using the heat recovered from CaL to produce additional steam that will drive a new steam turbine (there is no a detailed heat integration)	Retrofit of an existing subcritical power plant with a CaL system coupled with a new supercritical steam cycle
Carbonator	Operating temperature, °C F ₀ /F _{CO2} FCaO/FCO ₂ Ws, kg/MW or kg/m ² Ca conversion*, % CO ₂ capture efficiency, % Gas pressure drop, kPa Model used Others?	650°C F ₀ /F _R =0.01 8.74 kg solids/kg of CO ₂ captured Around 1000 kg/m ² 11.6 % of CaO conversion ~ 90 % 10 kPa Kunii and Levenspiel 1D model used by Abanades et al. (2004)	650°C F ₀ /F _{CO2} =0.03 (55 t/h of F ₀) F ₀ /F _R =0.01 F _{CaO} /F _{CO2} =3 - 20 % of CaO conversion 80 % of CO ₂ captured - There is no model implemented, it is assumed that X _N is achieved CaSO ₄ formation considered (99% of conversion)	650°C 45.7 kg/s of F ₀ F _{CaO} /F _{CO2} =7 - 11.4 % 80 % of CO ₂ captured Not specified CFB model developed by Hawthorne et al. (2008) Although in this paper it has been included the assumption that CaO available for carbonation can be sulfated up to X _{sulf}	650°C F ₀ /F _{CO2} =0.34 F _{CaO} /F _{CO2} =6.82 - 20 % of CaO conversion 85 % of CO ₂ captured - There is no a reactor model implemented	650°C F ₀ /F _{CO2} =0.1 (<i>See Notes below</i>) F _{CaO} /F _{CO2} =4-7 (for 70 to 90 % of CO ₂ capture, respectively) 1500-2000 kg/m ² 13-18 % of CaO conversion depending on the case 70-90 % of CO ₂ captured - Model developed by Alonso et al. (2009), but using the kinetic model of Grasa et al. (2009) and considering a sorbent capacity decay law for partially converted particles developed by Rodríguez et al. (2010). 100 % of SO ₂ reacts with CaO
Calciner	Operating temperature, °C Calcination efficiency, % O ₂ content in oxidant stream, % CO ₂ recycle, % O ₂ content in calciner flue gas, %	900°C 100 % of CaCO ₃ calcined 50 %(vol.) Not given 2.5 %(vol.)	900°C 100 % of CaCO ₃ calcined 100 %(vol.) 0 % Not specified	900°C 100 % of CaCO ₃ calcined 100 %(vol.) 0 % of rich-CO ₂ recirculated 3 %(vol.)	900°C 100 % of CaCO ₃ calcined 100 %(vol.) 0 % of rich-CO ₂ recirculated < 0.5 %(vol.) (calculated from the results published)	950°C 100 % of CaCO ₃ calcined Around 25 %(vol.) 60-63 % of rich-CO ₂ recirculated 2.5-3.0 %(vol.)

	Gas pressure drop, kPa Others?	20 kPa (0.2 bar) -	Not specified A 99.5 % of coal conversion is considered, while 100% of SO ₂ formed is captured due to the high Ca/S ratio	Not specified A 99.8 % of coal conversion is considered 89.1 % (vol.) of CO ₂ in the flue gas exiting the calciner	- Thermal efficiency of the calciner is considered to be 93 %	- A 99.6 % of coal conversion is considered while 100 % of SO ₂ formed is captured due to an extra CaCO ₃ make-up flow (with a Ca/S=3)			
Steam cycle	SH/RH pressure, bar SH/RH temperature, °C BFW temperature, °C Condensing pressure, bar Turbine isentropic efficiency HP/IP/LP, % Electric-mechanical efficiency, %	300 bar/ 54 bar 600°C/ 610°C 315°C Not given Not given 98.5 %	285 bar/59 bar 600°C/620°C 307°C Not given Not given Not given	300 bar/not given 600°C/not given Not specified Not specified Not specified	242 bar/42.5 bar 566°C/566°C 278.6°C 0.118 bar Not specified Not specified	280 bar/40 bar 600°C/600°C 285°C 0.045 bar - 100 %			
Air separation unit	Consumption for O ₂ production, kWh/tO ₂ O ₂ purity, % vol. Number of compression steps	- 97 % (vol) of O ₂	184.8 kWh/ton O ₂ 95 % (vol.) of O ₂	- 95.2 % (vol.) of O ₂ (N ₂ and Ar) Four steps (1.013 bar/2.5 bar/3.9 bar/6 bar) with IC	220 kWh/ton O ₂ (Metz et al., 2005) 95 % O ₂	160 kWh/ton O ₂ (Darde et al., 2009) Not specified			
CO ₂ compression and purification	Final CO ₂ pressure, bar Final CO ₂ purity, % Number of IC compressors Compressors isentropic efficiency, % Electric-mechanical efficiency, % Overall specific consumption, kJe/kgCO ₂	Not information specified of this stage	Not included in the analysis	110 bar 95.3 % (vol.) (The remaining gas is Ar, N ₂ and O ₂) 5 compressors with IC (3.15, 10.4, 31, 75 and 110 bar) Not specified Not specified Not specified	110 bar - - - - 0.4 GJ/tCO ₂ (111 kWh _e /tCO ₂) (Metz et al., 2005)	150 bar Not specified 5 stages with IC Not specified Not specified 100 kWh _e /tCO ₂ (Darde et al., 2009)			
Other auxiliaries	Fans polytropic efficiency, % Fans electric-mechanical efficiency, % Coal handling and milling, kJ/kg coal Limestone handling and milling, kJ/kg Ash handling, kJ/kg	80 % 94 % 30 kJ/kg coal 90 kJ/kg CaCO ₃ 100 kJ/kg ash	88 % (isentropic efficiency) 98 % Not considered Not considered Not considered	Not specified Not specified Not specified Not specified Not specified	Not specified Not specified Not specified Not specified Not specified	Not specified Not specified Not specified Not specified Not specified			
Results	Gross power, MW _e ASU consumption, MW _e CO ₂ compression consumption, MW _e Fans consumptions, MW _e	579.4 MW _e 48.1 MW _e 48.6 MW _e 10.4 MW _e	1737.8 MW _e 80.9 MW _e Not included 20.95 MW _e (carbonator)	2100.0 MW _e 126.5 MW _e Not included 20.95 MW _e (carbonator)	1875 MW _e (775 MW _e CaL) 115 MW _e 128 MW _e -	1000 MW _e (400 MW _e CaL) 62 MW _e 92 MW _e -	811.0 MW _e 63.1 MW _e 66 MW _e 15.4 MW _e	898.6 MW _e 73.9 MW _e 75.6 MW _e 16.3 MW _e	1048 MW _e 93.2 MW _e 90.1 MW _e 17.9 MW _e

	Auxiliaries (MWe) Net power, MW _e Net efficiency, % (Net output/heat of coal) CO ₂ capture ratio, % Credits for integration with cement industry** Specific CO ₂ emission, g/kWh	19.9 MW _e 452.4 MW _e 37.35 % (LHV) 97.04 % of CO ₂ captured Not enough information to be evaluated 27.4 g/kWh	51.6 MW _e 1584.3 MW _e 42.85 % 87.3 % 0.33 points (43.18 %) 103 g CO ₂ emitted/kWh net	53.9 MW _e 1898.6 MW _e 42.44 % 89.6 % 0.27 points (42.71 %) 86 g CO ₂ emitted/kWh net	99 MW _e from auxiliaries 1533 MW _e 39.24 % 88 % of total CO ₂ captured 0.86 points of increase (40.10 % of net efficiency) Not information available	- 846 MW _e 36.8 % (LHV) 93 % of total CO ₂ captured 2.8 points of increase (39.6 % of net efficiency) 74 g CO ₂ emitted/kWh net	9.9 MW _e 656.6 MW _e 32.4 % (LHV) 86.2 % 0.7 points (33.1 %) 156.3 g CO ₂ /kWh net	11.8 MW _e 721.0 MW _e 32.6 % (LHV) 91.5 % 0.6 points (33.2 %) 94.8 g CO ₂ /kWh net	15.0 MW _e 831.8 MW _e 32.9 % (LHV) 96.3 % 0.5 points (33.4 %) 41.0 g CO ₂ /kWh net
Comparison with reference plant w/o CO ₂ capture***	Efficiency penalty, % points Reduced specific emission, %	7.65 points of penalty Not information available	2.75 points of penalty 86.7 % reduction (774 g CO ₂ /kWh net existing plant)	3.16 points of penalty 88.9 % reduction (774 g CO ₂ /kWh net existing plant)	6.36 points of penalty (45.6 % in the reference plant) Not information available	8.3 points of penalty (45.1 % in the reference plant) 89.4 % reduction (696 g CO ₂ emitted /kWh net existing plant)	8.2 points (40.6 %) 81.8 % (857.3 g CO ₂ /kWh net)	8.3 points (40.9 %) 88.8 % (849.5 g CO ₂ /kWh net)	8.5 points (41.4 %) 95.1 % (838.7 g CO ₂ /kWh net)
Notes *Ca conversion referred to the unsulfated sorbent and defined as: $\frac{x_{CaO}}{x_{CaO} + x_{CaCO_3}}$ **Credits for cement industry have been evaluated as: $Credits = \left(\frac{Net\ power}{H_{coal,RP} + H_{coal,calciner} - H_{calc,F0} - Net\ efficiency} \right) \cdot 100$ H _{calc,F0} : Heat required to calcine the Ca contained in F ₀ (H _{calc} =182.9 MW/kmol) ***Reference plant has been considered as the existing one and a new one with the same fuel input as the calciner	Considering a 45 % of efficiency of an USC steam cycle from Czielska et al. (2009)	Two different modeling approaches to the carbonator are used. First approach assumes that CaO achieves its maximum conversion (X _{b,N}) (column left), and the second one evaluates CaO conversion according to the 1D model explained by Lasheras et al. (2011) (column right). 45.6 % of net efficiency in the reference plant <u>Fan consumption of calciner and CO₂ compression have not been included</u> in the efficiency provided.	In this work, <u>heat recovered from CO₂ compression stage has been integrated into the new steam cycle</u> , increasing net power output and therefore net efficiency of the system	Several methods for the utilization of the heat recovered from the CaL system are analyzed. It is concluded that the only option likely to be realized in a near future, as it does not affect the operation of the existing power plant, is to use the heat recovered from the CaL system to produce steam to drive a new steam cycle. Therefore, this is the option describe in this report.	In this work, the efficiency is analyzed when capturing 70 (left column), 80 (middle) and 90 % (right column) of CO ₂ in the carbonator for different F ₀ /F _{CO₂} ratios between 0.1 and 0.35. The highest efficiencies were obtained for the lowest make-up flows, that is F ₀ /F _{CO₂} =0.1, and therefore these are the cases analyzed here.				

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2 Calcium looping for pre-combustion capture applications

2.1 Modeling of SE-SMR reactors

Sorbent enhanced steam methane reforming (SE-SMR) is a process where a CO₂ sorbent is used in combination with a reforming catalyst to remove CO₂ within the reactor, thus shifting the equilibrium of the reforming reactions towards higher hydrogen yield. A number of papers have been reported where more or less sophisticated modeling of SE-SMR reactors have been performed. The details of some selected papers involving the use of CO₂ sorbents have been given in Table 3.

Different reactor concepts (packed bed (Chen et al, 2011, Martavaltzi et al, 2011, Li et al, 2007, Zagoruiko et al, 2007) and fluid bed (Wang et al, 2011-I, Wang et al, 2011-II, Wang et al, 2011-III, Di Carlo et al, 2010, Jakobsen et al, 2009, Lee et al, 2006)) as well as hybrid concepts including membranes (Chen et al, 2008, Fayyas et al, 2005) for in situ hydrogen removal and a special concept based on the combination of a fixed catalytic monolith together with a circulating particular sorbent (Koumpouras et al, 2007) have been studied. Mostly natural CaO sorbents such as limestone and dolomite are used, but also novel synthetic Ca, Li and hydrotalcite (HTC) based sorbents have been included to see the effect of sorbent properties on the process performance (Chen et al, 2011, Li et al, 2007, Jakobsen et al, 2009). Generally, for kinetics of the elementary reactions of steam reforming, the parameters derived by Xu & Froment have been used. (Xu et al, 1989) For the CaO carbonation reaction, some works rely on their own (apparent) kinetic constants derived from thermo gravimetric analyses, while others have used kinetic expressions and parameters from earlier work by Sun (Sun et al, 2008), Lee (Lee et al, 2004) or Bhatia. (Bhatia et al, 1983).

Fixed bed SE-SMR is typically modeled for temperatures from 500 to 650°C, pressures from 1 to 15 atm and for steam to methane ratios (S/M) from 2.0 to 5.5. In Chen et al. (2011) and Martavaltzi (2011), simple modeling of breakthrough curves have been carried out where the parameters needed for the particle conversion expressions have been derived from their own or literature thermo gravimetric measurements or isotherm data of the various sorbents. The temperature and pressure dependencies on the enhancement in hydrogen production are analyzed and hydrogen and CO₂ concentrations in the reactor effluent with time are modeled showing different behavior of the various sorbents. Only result from one (the first) cycle is presented.

Li et al also considered sorbent capacity decay with cycle number (Li et al, 2007). The dependency of the CaO conversion on cycle number derived by Grasa et al was used to model multi-cycle breakthrough curves as well as CO₂ evolution curves during regeneration from a packed bed reactor during cyclic SE-SMR operation (Grasa et al, 2006). CaO sorbents such as limestone, dolomite and impregnated CaO systems were compared. They conclude (obviously) that a synthesized sorbent with high performance and low cost would be highly beneficial for the process.

Zagoruiko et al focused on modeling the thermal effects by using a "moving heat wave" generated by in situ catalytic combustion of methane for regeneration of the sorbent (Zagoruiko et al, 2007). Both temperature and CO₂ concentration profiles throughout the fixed bed with time are modeled.

Fluid bed SE-SMR reactor modeling has been developed through a series of papers Wang et al using a 3D two fluid Eulerian hydrodynamic model together with kinetic parameters of the reactions taking place (Wang et al, 2011-I, Wang et al, 2011-II, Wang et al, 2011-III). No details on catalyst nor sorbent particle structure were included assuming only that the reactions takes place on the particle surface without diffusion limitations. Different gas flow rates show that higher rates give slightly lower methane conversions, lower hydrogen yield and lower CO₂ capture rate. The gas-particle flow within the reactor is simulated as well as the gas composition throughout the reactor. CO₂ sorption is fast compared with the rate of the reforming reactions while the CO₂ desorption rate is slow due to the increased CO₂ concentration in the gas phase making higher temperature needed to achieve the necessary kinetics of sorbents regeneration.

Di Carlo et al include both intra- and extra-particle mass transfer effects in their study of SE-SMR using a similar two fluid Eulerian model as Wang (Di Carlo et al, 2010, Wang et al, 2011-III). A modified shrinking core model (SCM) by Johnsen (Johnsen et al, 2006) was assumed. A Ni-catalyst/dolomite powder mixture was used. At sorbent/catalyst mass ratios larger than 2, autothermal conditions in the reactor were simulated where the heat produced upon sorption compensated the endothermicity of the reforming reaction. Particle segregation due to differences in particle fluidization properties of catalyst and sorbent particles was partly studied by assuming large difference in average particle size of the two. In this case no segregation was observed for gas velocities above a critical minimum.

Jakobsen (Jakobsen et al, 2009) studied the SE-SMR process by using a linear plug flow model for fluid bed reactor using different flow regimes and sorbents. Their results indicate that the contact time in a riser is too short to reach high methane conversion and CO₂ capture rates, while high hydrogen yield and capture rates can be obtained in a bubbling bed. In the riser simulations, best performance was obtained with Na₂ZrO₃ sorbent (92.6% H₂ and 3.0% CO₂ in gas effluent) while CaO gave a poorer performance due to slower kinetics (79.3 % H₂ and 11.5% CO₂ in effluent).

In none of the works dealing with modeling of SE-SMR in fluid bed reactors were degradation of the sorbent considered. In addition, modeling of the total cyclic process including both the reforming and calcination steps has to our knowledge not been done, not even in a simplistic way.

Table 3 - Summary of the assumptions and results of studies on reformer modeling

Source	Chen et al., Sci. China Tech. Sci., 54 (2011) 2999.	Martavaltzi et al., Ind. Eng. Chem. Res., 50 (2011) 539.	Li et al., Energy Fuel, 21 (2007) 2909.	Zagoruiko et al., React. Kinet. Catal. Lett., 91 (2007) 315.	Wang et al., Clean Techn. Environ. Policy, 13 (2011) 559.	Wang et al., Ind. Eng. Chem. Res., 50 (2010) 8430.
Particle conversion model/equation	$dX(\text{CaO})/dt=k_c(1-(t/(b+t)))^2$ $dX/dt = k_s (P_{\text{CO}_2} - P_{\text{CO}_2, \text{eq}})^n (1-X)^2$	$R = dX/dt = k_s S_{(X)} (1-X)^{2/3} (C_{\text{CO}_2} - C_{e, \text{CO}_2})^n$ $k_s = k_{s0} \exp(-E_a/RT)$	$dX/dt = k_c (1-X/X_u)^{2/3} (C_{\text{CO}_2} - C_{e, \text{CO}_2})^{(p/p_0)^{0.083}}$	$W_{\text{ads}} = 0.58 (p_{\text{CO}_2} - p_{e, \text{CO}_2}) (g_{\text{CO}_2} / g_{\text{CaO}}) (1/\text{atm sec})$	$R_a = dX/dt = 56k_s (1-X) (P_{\text{CO}_2} - P_{\text{CO}_2, \text{eq}})^n S$	$R_a = dX/dt = 56k_s (1-X) (P_{\text{CO}_2} - P_{\text{CO}_2, \text{eq}})^n S$
Sorbent capacity decay law	Not considered in the work	Not considered in the work	$X_{u,N} = (1/(1-X_r) + kN) + X_r$	Not considered in the work	Not considered in the work	Not considered in the work
Hydrodynamic regime of the reactor	Packed bed	Packed bed	Packed bed	Packed bed (?). Sorbent regeneration in a moving heat wave of a catalytic combustion reaction; 1D, homogeneous model with no diffusion restriction.	Bubbling fluidized bed	Bubbling fluidized bed
Hydrodynamic model	2D transient model	Plug flow, 1D	Plug flow		3D Eulerian two-fluid model	Eulerian two-fluid model
Particle distribution	Uniform, 6 mm	Uniform, 100-180 micron	200-425 m	1-2 mm spheres	Uniform, 500 micron, 1500kg/m ³	Uniform, 500 micron, 2400kg/m ³
Criteria for reactor dimensioning						
Superficial velocity, m/s	Not reported, unclear article	Lab scale	Lab scale	0.3 m/s	0.3-0.89m/s	0.32-0.89 m/s
Reactor height, m				1 m height	Height 0.4m	Height 0.34m
Others?					Diameter=0.2m	Diameter=0.14m
Governing parameters						
Temperature, °C	500,550,600 °C	T= 773-923K (500-650°C),	T= 923K (650°C)	T= 500°C	T=848K(575°C)	T=848K(575°C)
Pressure, bar	1-4 bar	P= 1 atm	15 atm	5 atm	P=1bar	P=1bar
S/C	S/C=2, 3.5, 4.5, 5.5	S/C= 3.4	S/C= 4	S/C= 3	S/C=3-5	S/C=5
F0/FCO2						
FR/FCO2						
Ws						
Results						
CO ₂ capture efficiency, %	Reaction run until breakthrough Dry H ₂ mole fraction >97%	Reflect experimental findings;	Modeling of multi-cycle breakthrough curves and CO ₂ evolution curves when regenerating. Verification		CO ₂ considered completely absorbed	CO ₂ considered completely absorbed

<p>H₂ yield, mol_{H₂}/mol_{NG}</p> <p>H₂ purity, %vol dry</p> <p>Pressure drop, kPa</p> <p>Others?</p>	<p>at lowest p and lowest S/C</p> <p>Best temp was 550°C</p>	<p>93% H₂ purity</p> <p>Carbonation rates at various temperatures predicted from model.</p>	<p>of model by experiments</p>		<p>0.96-0.98 dry H₂ yield depending on S/C</p>	<p>0.96-0.98 dry H₂ yield</p>
<p>Other notes</p>	<p>Various Li based sorbents are also evaluated</p>	<p>Commercial Ni-based catalyst.</p> <p>Impregnated CaO sorbent.</p> <p>Best temp 650°C due to sorption kinetics.</p>	<p>Limestone, dolomite and impregnated CaO compared.</p>	<p>Only interest in temperature profile through the bed during reforming and during (counter-current) regeneration</p>	<p>S/C=4 assumed to be optimum for SE-SMR</p>	

Source	Wang et al., Int. J. Greenhouse Gas Contr., 5 (2011) 489.	Di Carlo et al., Ind. Eng. Chem. Res., 49 (2010) 1561.	Jakobsen et al., Energy Proc., 1 (2009) 725.	Lee et al., Int. J. Hydr. Energ., 31 (2006) 649.	Koumpouras et al., Chem. Eng. Sci., 62 (2007) 2833.	Chen et al., Chem. Eng. Sci., 63 (2008) 170.	Fayyas et al., Ind. Eng. Chem. Res., 44 (2005) 9398.
Particle conversion model/equation	$R_a = dX/dt = 56k_s(1-X)(P_{CO_2}-P_{CO_2,eq})^n S$	$S_{carb} = \epsilon_d \rho_d M_{CO_2} (6/d_d(1-X))^{1/3} (1/RT)(P_{CO_2}-P_{e,CO_2})^{0.66} / (1/k_3 + (d_d/2)((1-X)^{1/3} - (1-X)^{2/3})/D_e + (1-X)^{2/3}/(h_{CO_2(gd)}))$ $k_3 = k_{s0} \exp(-E_d/RT)$	$dX/dt = M_{CaO} k_s (1-X/X_u)^m (P_{CO_2}-P_{e,CO_2})^n S$ $k_s = k_{s0} \exp(-E_d/RT)$	$r_{cbn} = dX/dt = (k_c/M_{CaO})(1-X/X_u)^2$	$r_{ads} = k_{LDF} (q^*_{CO_2} - q_{CO_2})$ Langmuir	$r = k_{11} (1-X_{CaO})^{0.67} (C_{CO_2} - C_{e,CO_2})$	$r_{ads} = dC_s/dt = k_a (C_{seq} - C_s)$ Langmuir
Sorbent capacity decay law	Not considered in the work	Not considered in the work	Not considered in the work	Not considered in the work	Not considered in the work	Not considered in the work	Not considered in the work
Hydrodynamic regime of the reactor	Bubbling fluidized bed	Bubbling fluidized bed	Bubbling fluidized bed	Moving bed reactor where sorbent and catalyst move co-current with gas	Riser where sorbent particles are transported through a static catalytic monolith	Fluidized bed & Fluidized bed membrane reactor (Pd)	Hybrid adsorbent-membrane reactor, Packed bed, Porous ceramic membrane
Hydrodynamic model	3D non-axisymmetric two-fluid model	2D Eulerian-eulerian two-fluid model	Plug flow. 1D reactor kinetic model		Riser		Plug flow
Particle distribution	Uniform, 500 micron, 1500kg/m ³	200-500 m	Uniform, 150 m	Uniform, 3 mm pellets	Uniform, 55 m	Uniform, 100 m	?
Criteria for reactor dimensioning Superficial velocity, m/s Reactor height, m Others?	0.3 m/s Height 4m Diameter=0.2m	0.3 m/s 0.6 m	0.05-1 m/s 0.679 m height	0.014 m/s	0.46 m/s 1 m height	1.7 m/s 4 m height	0.04 m/s
Governing parameters Temperature, °C Pressure, bar S/C F0/FCO2 FR/FCO2 Ws	T=848K(575°C) P=1, and 10bar S/C=5	T= 873-993K (600-720°C), P= 1 atm S/C= 3.4 Dolomite/catalyst= 0-5	T= 873K (600°C) P= 1 atm S/C= 4	T= 700°C 3 atm S/C= 3	T= 723-823K (450-550°C) 5 atm S/C= 6	T= 823 and 873K (550 and 600°C) 10 and 20 atm S/C= 3	T= 400 & 480°C 3 atm S/C= 3
Results				94% H2	Up to 98.5% CO2 recovery		

CO ₂ capture efficiency, % H ₂ yield, mol _{H₂} /mol _{NG} H ₂ purity, %vol dry Pressure drop, kPa Others?	>99% (at 1bar) >99% (at 1bar)	>93% H ₂ purity	98.7-99.9 % H ₂ purity	2.5% CO 1.3% CO ₂ 2.2% CH ₄	Up to 79% methane conv.	Up to 90% CO ₂ capture Membrane increases H ₂ yield and CO ₂ capture rate	
Other notes		Dolomite used as sorbent Particle segregation studied using different cat/sorb mixtures Temperature of outlet gas	Dolomite used as sorbent Riser (2 m/s) give 75-79% H ₂ purity and low CO ₂ capture.			Sorbent + membrane assisted reforming Effect of membrane	"Adsorption system"... no details on kind of sorbent...

2.2 Process modeling

The process most widely assessed for pre-combustion CO₂ capture by CaO sorption is sorption-enhanced steam methane reforming (SE-SMR). According to this concept, methane is converted in a single reactor where CO₂ is adsorbed over a solid sorbent while SMR and WGS reactions occur. Therefore, progression of the SMR and WGS gaseous phase reactions is not limited to equilibrium set by CO₂ formation and can proceed almost to a complete depletion of reactants.

The enthalpy balance of the overall reaction is only 14.5 kJ/mol, meaning that it is well thermally balanced, and therefore not only the carbonation reaction facilitates hydrogen production by removing CO₂ from the gaseous phase, but also provides the heat required for the steam reforming reaction, allowing for the use of adiabatic reformers.

In Figure 1, some results from equilibrium calculations of a SE-SMR reactor with abundance of solid sorbent are shown. The result of the contemporaneity of SMR, WGS and carbonation reactions is a temperature range (roughly 500-650°C, at atmospheric pressure) with stable H₂ yield and CO₂ capture ratio. Higher temperatures lead to a reduced progression of carbonation reaction, while lower temperatures lead to Ca(OH)₂ formation, with negative effects related to the removal of H₂O from the gaseous phase and a reduction of the effective S/C. Apart from temperature, steam to carbon ratio and pressure are the parameters which mostly affect the process. In particular, high pressures require higher temperatures (650-750°C, at 25 bar) and higher S/C to obtain H₂ yields and CO₂ capture ratios similar to atmospheric pressure values.

Figure 3 - Influence of temperature, pressure and steam to carbon ratio on hydrogen yield and CO₂ capture ratio in a SE-SMR process. The dot dashed curves in the upper diagram refer to a conventional SMR process carried out at 3.5 steam to carbon ratio.

An important issue of SE-SMR processes is sorbent regeneration, to be carried out via calcination reaction. Decomposition of CaCO₃ into CaO and CO₂ can be obtained either by increasing temperature (temperature swing) or by reducing the CO₂ partial pressure (pressure swing) by an actual depressurization or by means of steam purging. In any case, thermal power is required in the calcination step to provide the heat for the endothermic calcination reaction. Heat can be provided either by means of heat exchangers or by direct combustion in the calciner. In the second case, calcination has to be carried out by means of oxy-fuel combustion to avoid dilution of the CO₂ released from calcination with nitrogen.

Different options can be considered for design of the reactors. The most feasible option is to consider low pressure interconnected fluidized bed reactors. The feasibility of this option has been demonstrated for other processes (post-combustion Ca-looping, CLC, sorption enhanced gasification of biomass) in a number of pilot installations. Therefore, technology breakthrough is not expected to be relevant for the application of the SE-SMR process. The limit of this layout is related to the low pressure of the H₂ delivered, which would require relevant energy penalty associated to cooling and compression in case of a high pressure final utilization (e.g. combustion in a gas turbine, utilization in high pressure refinery processes).

The use of pressurized interconnected fluidized bed is an alternative investigated in some works. However, two kind of problems arise with such a configuration: (i) stable operations of interconnected pressurized fluidized beds has not been demonstrated yet and requires

technology breakthrough and (ii) regeneration temperatures rise with pressure up to values (roughly 1100-1200°C, at 20-30 bar) at which the activity of the catalyst and the capacity of the sorbent are compromised.

A further alternative are packed beds, which allow operating reforming and calcination at different pressures by keeping the solid material always in the same reactor, periodically exposed to atmospheres favorable to carbonation and to calcination. The intrinsic dynamic behavior of the system, the difficult control of peak temperatures and the complexity and cost of high temperature valve system represent the limits of the packed bed-based process.

A summary of the process simulation studies on SE-SMR from the open literature is reported in Table 1. Two studies (Chen et al, 2011; Fernandez et al., 2012) assessed only the SE-SMR reactors system. Chen et al. (2011) focused on interconnected fluidized beds. Fernandez et al. (2012) considered the innovative Cu-Ca looping process based on fixed beds, where calcination is sustained by oxidation of fuel by means of a CLC loop using Cu/CuO as oxygen carrier. Ochoa- Fernández et al. (2007) assessed a complete plant for hydrogen production based on high pressure (10 bar) reforming and low pressure (1 bar) regeneration. Solieman et al. (2009) and Romano et al. (2011) considered the integration of SE-SMR process into a combined cycle based power plant. In the first case, a packed bed system was considered, while pressurized interconnected fluidized beds were adopted in the second case. Finally, Meyer et al. (2011) assessed the process based on the ZEG concept, where the H₂-rich gas is converted in a high temperature SOFC and the waste heat from the fuel cell is used to regenerate the Ca-based sorbent.

In all the cases, reactors have been calculated at equilibrium, which is a reasonable assumption according to experimental data and outputs from reactor modeling studies. Reforming was assumed to be carried out at 550-600°C and S/C=2.5-3.5 for low pressure (1-2 bar) reformers cases and at 600-700°C and S/C=4.2-4.8 for high pressure (17-35 bar) cases. In none of these plants sorbent purging and makeup have been considered. This appears to be a reasonable assumption when feeding a clean gaseous fuel as natural gas, with no ash and negligible sulfur, considering that no impurity is expected to accumulate in the Ca-loop or to affect the capacity and the activity of the Ca-sorbent (in case of CaO, sorbent capacity loss is a consequence of calcination conditions, there is no need of using a fuel with sulfur or ashes). For this reason the Ca conversion in the reformer cannot overcome the residual capacity of the sorbent after many carbonation-calcination cycles. Conversion between 10 and 53% has been adopted in these studies, significantly higher than the residual capacity of natural sorbents, but acceptable considering the possible advancements in the development of synthetic sorbents and reactivation techniques.

Overall H₂ yields of 2.4-2.7 molH₂/molCH_{4-eq} (or 0.60-0.68 molH₂/molH_{2-eq})¹ and cold gas efficiencies of 81-83% have been obtained in all the cases. In cases for power production, net efficiencies of 50-51% have been obtained when using state of the art combined cycles, while and efficiency of 76.9% is claimed for the SOFC-based ZEG concept.

¹ Equivalent CH₄ and H₂ concentrations in a gas stream are referred to the capacity of H₂ generation by SMR and WGS reactions and are defined as follows:

$$x_{\text{CH}_4\text{-eq}} = x_{\text{CH}_4} + 7/4x_{\text{C}_2\text{H}_6} + \dots + (1/2m+1/8n)x_{\text{C}_m\text{H}_n}$$

$$x_{\text{H}_2\text{-eq}} = 4x_{\text{CH}_4} + 7x_{\text{C}_2\text{H}_6} + \dots + (2m+1/2n)x_{\text{C}_m\text{H}_n} + x_{\text{CO}} + x_{\text{H}_2} + 2x_{\text{C}}$$

Table 4 – Main assumptions and results from process simulation studies on SE-SMR technology

Source	Ochoa-Fernández et al., 2007	Solieman et al., 2009	Chen et al., 2011	Romano et al., 2011	Meyer et al., 2011	Fernandez, al., 2012
Fuel	100% CH4	100% CH4	100% CH4	NG (15.5 gC/MJLHV)	NG (15.7 gC/MJLHV)	100% CH4
Final product	Hydrogen @ 25 bar	Power	Hydrogen @ 2 bar	Power	Power	Hydrogen @35 bar / Power
<u>Reformer-Carbonator</u>						
Type of reactor	Packed bed	Packed bed	Generic fluidized bed	CFB	turbulent bed (u0=1m/s)	Packed bed
Reactor model	Chemical equilibrium, no Ca(OH) ₂ formation	Chemical equilibrium	Chemical equilibrium	Chemical equilibrium	Chemical equilibrium (validated with a BFB reactor model)	Chemical equilibrium
Adiabatic/cooled	Adiabatic	Adiabatic	Adiabatic	Cooled	Adiabatic	Adiabatic
Operating temperature, °C	575	600	550	700	600	650
Operating pressure, bar	10	17	2	25	2	35
S/C	3	4.2	3.5	4.5	2.5	4.8
F0/FCO2	0	-	0	0	-	-
FCa/FCO2	1.5	-	9.2	5.8	-	-
Catalyst	-	1%wt. Noble metal on alumina	-	-	-	-
Catalyst/carrier/Ca ratio	-	0.5:1:1 (wt.)	-	-	-	-
Ca conversion, %	52.83	>14	11.1	15	32	34.8
CO2 capture efficiency, %	79.2	85	91.1	86.5	-	86.9
CH4 conversion, %	79.4	N/A	-	88.0	-	88.3
H2 yield, molH2/molCH4eq_ref	3.18	-	3.68	3.48	-	3.52
H2 yield, molH2/molH2eq_ref	0.79	-	0.92	0.87	-	0.88
H2 purity, %vol dry	93.9	-	98	94.7	-	96.4
Prereforming	none	-	none	none	none	none
<u>Calciner</u>						
Type of reactor	Packed bed	Packed bed	Generic fluidized bed	CFB	BFB (u0=0.4 m/s) - steam as fluidizing gas	Packed bed
Reactor model	Chemical equilibrium	Chemical equilibrium	Chemical equilibrium	Chemical equilibrium	Chemical equilibrium	Chemical equilibrium
Operating temperature, °C	870	820	900	1200	800	830
Operating pressure, bar	1	1	2	25	2	1
xCO2 out calciner	52.0	-	-	59.9	-	49.0
S (added)/CO2	0	1.8	0.02	0	-	0.36
Heat source	CH4 oxycombustion, with EGR	-	CH4 oxycombustion	NG oxycombustion, with EGR	Heat exchange from SOFC waste heat	CuO reduction with CH4
Heat input to calciner, %LHV	33.5	-	27.1	29	0	31.3
Calcination efficiency, %	100	-	100	100	-	100

Source	Ochoa-Fernández et al., 2007	Soliman et al., 2009	Chen et al., 2011	Romano et al., 2011	Meyer et al., 2011	Fernandez, al., 2012
<u>Overall balance</u>						
H2 yield, molH2/moltotCH4eq	2.72	-	2.68	2.47	-	2.42
H2 yield, molH2/molH2eq	0.68	-	0.67	0.62	-	0.60
Cold gas efficiency, %LHV	82.2	-	81.1	83.1	-	81.2
Final CO2 purity, %	99.36	-	>99	96.12	100	100
Overall CO2 capture ratio, %	100	-	-	88	100	87.6
<u>Power island</u>	-	Combined cycle	-	Combined cycle: F-class GT; 3L SC (130/27/4 bar, 565/565°C)	ZEG concept: SOFC @ 1000°C, patm, 0.732V, 0.251A/cm2 + 550°C bottoming steam cycle	Combined cycle
Final CO2 pressure, bar	1	110	-	150	110	-
Gross power, MWe	-	-	-	464.8	402.1	-
Aux. Consumption, MWe	33.6	-	-	45.7	29.3	-
Net power, MWe	-	-	-	419.2	372.8	-
Net efficiency, %	-	50.8	-	50.19	76.9	-
Specific CO2 emission, g/kWhe	-	-	-	49.2	0	-
Specific CO2 emission, g/Nm3_H2	0	-	-	-	-	100.3
Efficiency penalty, % points	-	-	-	-8.4	-	-
CO2 avoided, %	-	-	-	85.95	100	-
SPECCA, MJ/kgCO2	-	-	-	3.42	-	-

The application of SE-SMR process has been proposed also for coal-fed power plants. In this case, coal is gasified with a H₂-rich recycled stream in a hydrogasifier, where carbon is converted into a CH₄-rich syngas to be sent to two stages of reforming/carbonation, where H₂ is produced and CO₂ captured. The H₂-based syngas is then converted into electric power by a high temperature SOFC (ZECA concept), by a semi-closed internal combustion steam cycle, based on H₂ oxycombustion (Zecomix concept), or by a combined cycle (Zecomag layout). Such a process has a much higher complexity than the NG-fed one and large uncertainties exist on the feasibility of the process. In particular, (i) the use of a fuel rich of ash, sulfur and other impurities which will affect the performance of the sorbent and probably prevent the use of synthetic sorbents, (ii) the need of 4 interconnected gas-solid reactors (hydrogasifier + two carbonators + calciner) operating at high pressure (at least the hydrogasifier and one carbonator), (iii) the need of exotic components for gas cleaning, solids handling and power generation, make this process extremely complex even in a long term view.

A few studies assessed this process with sufficient details, whose assumptions and results are reported in Table 2. Optimistic assumptions, typical of a long term view, have been necessarily made in these studies, mainly related to the sorbent performance, for which very high activities have been assumed despite the harsh operating conditions.

Source	Perdikaris et al., 2009	Calabrò et al., 2008		Romano and Lozza, 2010a/b		
Fuel	Coal (25.3 gC/MJLHV)	Coal (24.7 gC/MJLHV)		Coal (26.2 gC/MJLHV)		
<u>Hydrogasifier</u>						
Operating pressure, bar	60	30		66.5		
Recycle ratio, %	70	70		66.7		
Operating temperature, °C	795	-		800		
C conversion, %	95	-		99		
<u>Reformers - carbonators</u>						
Type of reactor	Generic fluidized bed	Generic fluidized bed		Generic fluidized bed		
Reactor model	Chemical equilibrium	Chemical equilibrium		Chemical equilibrium		
Adiabatic/cooled	Adiabatic	Adiabatic		Adiabatic		
Operating temperature, °C	770 / 670	750 / 600		883 / 781		
Operating pressure, bar	60.5 / 4	30 / 30		65.2 / 63.9		
S/C: C=CH4+CO+CO2	1.2 / 0.61	-		2 / 3		
F0/FC of inlet coal	0.132	-		0.17		
FCa/FC: C=CH4+CO+CO2	2.66	-		0.85 / 1.67		
Ca conversion, %	30	100		50		
CO2 capture efficiency, %	89	94.6		94.7		
<u>Calciner</u>						
Type of reactor	Generic fluidized bed - CO2 as fluidizing gas	Generic fluidized bed		Moving bed		
Reactor model	Chemical equilibrium	Chemical equilibrium		Chemical equilibrium		
Operating temperature, °C	900	950	1200	1250	920	1250
Operating pressure, bar	2	1	30	70	1	70
xCO2 out calciner	100	-	-	80.6	-	82.1
Heat source	Heat from combustion of SOFC anode gas	Coal oxycombustion	Syngas oxycombustion	Pet coke oxycombustion with EGR	Coal oxycombustion with EGR	Pet coke oxycombustion with EGR
% total fuel to calciner	-	28.1	-	33	31.2	32.7
Calcination efficiency, %	-	100	100	100	100	100
<u>Overall balance</u>						
H2 yield, molH2/molH2eq	-	Plant 1	Plant 2	Case A	Case D	-
Cold gas efficiency, %LHV	-	62.7	50.3	71.6-74.7	75.2	73.8
Final CO2 purity, %	100	-	-	95.4	-	98.2
Overall CO2 capture ratio, %	89	100	100	100	100	95

Source	Perdikaris et al., 2009	Calabrò et al., 2008		Romano and Lozza, 2010a/b		ZECOMAG concept: advanced combined cycle (1500°C TIT gas turbine + USC bottoming steam cycle)
<u>Power Island</u>	ZECA concept: SOFC @ 900°C, 1.2 bar, 0.74V, 0.25A/cm ² , Uf=57.5% + bottoming steam cycle	ZECOMIX concept: HT 1400°C TIT steam cycle based on H ₂ /O ₂ combustion + USC (200 bar, 600°C) bottoming cycle		ZECOMIX concept: HT 1400°C TIT steam cycle based on H ₂ /O ₂ combustion + USC (247 bar, 600°C) bottoming cycle		
Gross power, MWe	100	33.91	9.55	886.2	870.2	614.02
Aux. Consumption, MWe	12.41	14.9	3.01	218.7	241.4	81.0
Net power, MWe	87.59	19.01	6.54	667.5	628.8	533.0
Net efficiency, %	40	45.9	21.9	46.69	44.37	46.74
Specific CO ₂ emission, g/kWhe	150	0	0	0	0	33.8
Efficiency penalty, % points	-	-	-	-6.64	-8.96	-6.59
CO ₂ avoided, %	-	-	-	100	100	94.49
SPECCA, MJ/kgCO ₂	-	-	-	1.57	2.22	1.64

Table 5 – Main assumptions and results from process simulation studies on coal hydrogasification and SE-SMR technology (ZECA – Zecomix/Zecomag)

The last application considered in the literature for pre-combustion CO₂ capture with Ca-based sorbents is sorption enhanced gasification. In this process, a solid fuel is gasified at high pressure in the presence of a Ca-based sorbent, which removes the CO₂ from the gaseous phase favoring hydrogen production and provides the heat for the endothermic gasification reaction. A relevant fraction of the coke (50-80%) is not converted in the gasifier but is sent into the regenerator reactor together with CaCO₃. By blowing pure O₂ in the regenerator, coke is oxidized providing the heat for calcination and producing a CO₂-rich exhaust gas.

Source	Lin et al., 2005	Weimer et al., 2008
Fuel	Coal (25.4 gC/MJLHV)	Lignite (30.7 gC/MJLHV)
Final product	Hydrogen	Power
Gasifier		
Type of reactor	-	-
Reactor model	Chemical equilibrium	Chemical equilibrium
Adiabatic/cooled	Adiabatic	Adiabatic
Operating temperature, °C	650	750
Operating pressure, bar	30	20
S/C (S added)	2.0	0
F ₀ /F _C of inlet coal	0.10	0.21
FCa/FC	0.72	3.26
Ca conversion, %	63.2	24.5
CO ₂ capture efficiency, %	80.0	94.6
C conversion, %	53	80
H ₂ yield, molH ₂ /molH ₂ eq	0.43	0.45
H ₂ purity, %vol dry	90.6	95.5
Calciner		
Type of reactor	-	-
Reactor model	Chemical equilibrium	Chemical equilibrium
Operating temperature, °C	1100	920
Operating pressure, bar	1	1
xCO ₂ out calciner	85.3	100
S (added)/CO ₂	0	0
Heat source	Oxycomb of unconv. C from gasifier with EGR	Oxycomb of unconv. C from gasifier
% total fuel to calciner	-	-
Calcination efficiency, %	94.2	100
Overall balance		
H ₂ yield, molH ₂ /molH ₂ eq	0.43	0.45
Cold gas efficiency, %LHV	70.2	65.0
Final CO ₂ purity, %	-	-
Overall CO ₂ capture ratio, %	89.5	95.6
Power island		
	-	Combined cycle with assumed 58%LHV electric efficiency + steam cycle for waste heat recovery with 46% efficiency
Final CO ₂ pressure, bar	-	-
Gross power, MWe	-	489
Aux. Consumption, MWe	-	100.3
Net power, MWe	-	388.7
Net efficiency, %	-	42.0 (38.9)
Specific CO ₂ emission, g/kWhe	-	39.4

Table 6 - Main assumptions and results from process simulation studies on sorption enhanced coal gasification.

2.2.1 Guidelines for future works

On the basis of the modeling and experimental findings, the following modeling guidelines and needs of experimental investigation can be highlighted:

Ca utilization can have an important influence on the performance of all the processes considered, affecting the final efficiency by several % points (Romano and Lozza

2010a). In applications where sorbent must be purged to avoid ash buildup and sorbent contamination by formation of stable sulfur species, it is highly probable that natural sorbents will be preferred from an economic point of view. Therefore, deactivation curves considering the average number of carbonation calcination cycles experienced by the sorbent can be used to estimate the sorbent capacity, as implemented by Weimer et al. (2008). However, most of the experimental activity on sorbent cyclic stability has been carried out focusing on post-combustion applications. Therefore, experimental activity on the capacity and reactivity of natural sorbents at conditions closer to pre-combustion applications is required.

On the contrary, in NG-fed SE-SMR plants, no sorbent contamination is expected and synthetic materials can be used. For this reason, higher capacities can be reasonably assumed, also considering the expected progresses in the synthesis of artificial sorbents. It can however be highlighted that, due to the relatively high uncertainty of the performance of natural and synthetic sorbents at the actual process conditions, sensitivity analyses on sorbent capacity represent an important added value for every process simulation study.

In plants for H₂ production, it is important to include the PSA process for H₂ purification within the process model as done by Ochoa-Fernandez et al. (2007). As a matter of facts, PSA process can have a relevant effect on the mass and energy balance since PSA off-gas, rich of CO, CO₂, CH₄ and a part of the H₂ (10-20%, according to the hydrogen recovery factors of commercial PSA) can be recycled to the calciner. These gases, burned with O₂, provide part of the heat for regeneration in case of oxycombustion-based regeneration, reducing the required primary fuel input.

Modeling needs for PSA can also be highlighted. It is important to understand the hydrogen recovery factor obtainable when a syngas with a very low content of carbon species from SE-SMR is processed in a PSA. Since the N₂/H₂ ratio (associated to N₂ content in natural gas) is not improved by SE-SMR process and N₂ is often the limiting species in commercial PSA applications, it is possible that hydrogen recovery factor cannot be significantly improved despite the higher initial purity. For this reason, SE-SMR process can take advantage from the development of new PSA sorbents more active towards N₂ than towards carbon species.

When comparing SE-SMR with conventional processes for H₂ production, it is important to consider the pressure at which H₂ is needed by the final user. As a matter of facts, homogeneous H₂ delivery pressures should be assumed when comparing different technologies. Penalties for SE-SMR-based layouts using low pressure reactors will arise when high pressure H₂ is needed.

Ca/catalyst ratio can be important for the mass and energy balance. Ni-based catalysts are thermal ballast and can behave as oxygen carrier between calciner and reformer. This phenomenon should be minimized since O₂ produced at high cost with ASU may react with Ni in the calciner to form NiO and eventually oxidize part H₂-rich syngas in the reformer. Therefore, low catalyst/Ca ratios are desirable.

A lack of modeling and experimental activity to find the minimum catalyst/sorbent ratio can be highlighted.

In case of regeneration by heat exchange, it is important to provide sufficient details on the heat and mass balances (a good example on this issue is the work by Perdikaris et al., 2009). As a matter of facts, heat transfer of high thermal power at high temperature under relatively low ΔT s is a critical process which can lead to large heat transfer surface operating at high temperature and relatively low fuel utilizations, voltages and efficiency of the fuel cell of the ZEC/ZECA concepts.

When calculating power plants based on gas turbines, it is important to use a reliable model for the gas turbine. As reported by Romano and Lozza (2010a), considering blades cooling flows can have a really important effect on the estimated overall plant efficiency when adopting advanced high TIT gas turbines (of the order of 4-5% points).

2.3 References

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3 Calcium looping applications on cement production plants

Cement is a key construction material, and global demand of cement is expected to grow at around six percent in 2012, amounting to 3.8 billion tons (CW Group, 2012). Cement industry, one of major CO₂ emission source in industry, accounts for 8% out of global CO₂ emission in 2011 (Olivier et al., 2012). Carbon emission reduction by more efficient use of fuel is possible but highly limited to an extent of half of its CO₂ emission since significant CO₂ is generated by calcination reaction as well as fuel combustion. Therefore, it is essential to retrofit a carbon capture process into cement plant if more than 90% reduction of carbon emission at cement plants would be targeted.

The most conventional capture technologies for cement plants are thought to be amine process and oxy-combustion since they are considered mature technology or at least ready to be implemented shortly. But it is likely that an amine process applied to cement plant would have higher energy penalty than those with power plant since a separate steam boiler is needed for steam supply to solvent regeneration stripper. If the separate steam cycle could be built in a way of having such a high complexity as one found in coal-fired power plants, similar energy penalty can be expected but no one would build a steam cycle with such a high complexity for the purpose of carbon capture. In case of oxy-combustion, there has been a concern that clinker quality may be affected by a kiln condition under oxy-combustion. Therefore, up to now, it is generally accepted that oxy-combustion cannot be applied to kiln but only pre-calciner, which significantly limits carbon capture rate in overall (IEA, 2008).

It has been argued that Ca-looping processes would have lower net energy consumption than amine processes since heat of reaction can be recovered by generating steam and running a steam cycle due to their relatively higher operating temperature. Ca-looping processes may be even more advantageous when integrated with cement plants than those combined with any other industrial plants in that their by-products, purge flow from calciner which is needed to maintain sorbent activity, can be potentially used as kiln feed while they must be dumped as waste or transferred to other sites in a distance for reuse when combined with power plants.

Since ECRA (2007) listed Ca-looping technologies as one of the promising capture technologies for cement plants, there have been conceptual studies which proposed various integration models, such as utilization of purge flow for the cement clinker and synergy between cement and power plants (Bosoaga et al., 2009; Naranjo et al., 2011). Rodriguez et al. (2011) proposed a way of producing CO₂ from calciner by indirect heating using hot CaO circulating between calciner and external combustor instead of oxy-combustion. The proposed design tackles CO₂ emission resulting from limestone calcinations only, which accounts for around 60% CO₂ emission, and is not effective for CO₂ emission relating to fuel combustion. To

enhance the performance, it was also suggested that the hot streams leaving the capture system could be utilized as heat source for electricity generation. It should be noted that there is no carbonator in this design as distinct from the regular Ca-looping configuration so the CO₂ that both external combustor and kiln generate cannot be recovered in the process, which means that this process would be worth considering only if a moderate level of CO₂ capture is adequate. The key operating parameters and performances in this process are presented in Table 7.

Even though it was conceivable in earlier studies that the purge CaO could be sent to kiln to make a clinker, there has been an issue that the deactivated CaO may deteriorate clinker quality and the factors which can potentially limit or affect the re-use of purge CaO have been discussed (Dean et al., 2011a). The study raised issues that sulphur conveyed by a purge stream can lead to expansion and cracking of the cement paste upon hydration and also affects formation of cement phases. Moreover, the trace elements released from fuel combustion in the calciner as well as attrition and agglomeration have been identified to be another potential issue in using purge materials. In the latter work of this group, it has been shown experimentally that the cement can be successfully produced from the purge by utilizing CaO experienced many cycles of calcination and carbonation (Dean et al., 2011b).

Given the postulate that the calciner purge can be used as kiln feed, a symbiosis model of a power plant, a Ca-looping process and a cement plant has been proposed with its mass and energy balances (Romeo et al., 2011). The flue gases from both plants are sent to the Ca-looping process, and the CaO purge of this capture unit is returned to cement plant, mixed with CaO from fresh raw material, and used as kiln feed. In this way, the CO₂ emission and energy consumption of the cement plant can be drastically reduced due to reduced calcinations load. The surplus energy from the capture unit can be utilized to generate electricity by running a separate steam cycle. A pinch analysis has been conducted in order to recover maximum energy from carbonator, solid purge, clean flue gases and CO₂ stream before compression. Part of this electricity has been used for CO₂ compression and air separation units. The total thermal energy consumption increases by about 6.7% for the integrated system due to addition of capture unit. CO₂ emission avoided was estimated to be 94% on a basis of total CO₂ emission at both industries by this integration system, which would add about 12.4 €/ton of avoided CO₂.

A similar assessment has been performed by Romano et al. (2012), who considered the effect of the actual composition of the purge on the maximum “substitution rate” of the cement plant raw meal. As a matter of fact, large amount of CaSO₄ and ashes from coal combustion in the calciner can limit the maximum amount of CaL purge that can be used in the cement plant. Such a maximum “substitution rate” strongly depends on the fuel used in the calciner and on the parameters of the CaL process.

As a direct integration of Ca-looping with a cement plant, Rodriguez et al. (2012) investigated two alternative processes with economic study of both. One is a retrofit replacing the existing pre-calciner with an oxy-calciner which can achieve 89% CO₂ capture and the other is capturing CO₂ from the kiln gas using a carbonator in addition to capturing CO₂ by oxy-calciner to improve capture rate up to 99%. As similar with other Ca-looping processes, the surplus energies from high temperature streams are recovered by integrated steam cycle. It is reported that the total energy consumption of cement plant increases from 2.93 GJ/ton of cement covering the electricity demand to 5.45 GJ/ton of cement by retrofit for carbon capture.

Ca-looping process can also be applied to a gas stream downstream of pre-calciner for over 90% capture. Flue gas stream leaving the 3rd preheater stage has been identified to be an optimum feed for a carbonator rather than the end-of-pipe flue gas, since it does not require preheating, has higher CO₂ partial pressure and lower volumetric flow rate (Ozcan et al., in preparation). The CO₂-depleted gas is routed back to 2nd preheater for raw material heating. The effects of sulfidation and ash have been taken into account in the carbonator model. It has been represented that this process is capable of achieving more than 90% CO₂ capture with additional energy consumption of 2.3 to 3.0 GJ/ton CO₂ avoided by considering heat recovery.

Table 7 - Summary of process configuration models on integration of Ca-looping process with cement plants.

Authors	Rodriguez et al. (2011)	Rodriguez et al. (2012)	Ozcan et al. (in preparation)	Romeo et al. (2011)
Type of integration	Hot CaO circulates between calciner and CFB combustor. There is no carbonator in the scheme.	Kiln gas is sent to carbonator for carbon capture. All CaCO ₃ from carbonator and fresh limestone are calcined in one common calciner.	Flue gases from the 3 rd preheater stage are diverted to Ca-looping process. The CO ₂ -depleted gas from the carbonator is routed back to the 2 nd preheater.	The industrial symbiosis of cement and power plants through Ca-looping process has been proposed. The flue gases from both power and cement plants are fed to the Ca-looping process.
Capacity of reference plant	3000 ton cement/day	3000 ton cement/day	3000 ton cement/day	3000 ton cement/day 500 MWe power plant
Fuel (existing plant and calciner) <i>Composition</i>	Petroleum coke used in CFB combustor [wt%]: C: 82.2 H: 3.1 O: 0.5 S: 5.5 N: 1.9 Ash: 0.3 Moisture: 6.5	Petroleum coke used in cement kiln and calciner [wt%]: C: 82.2 H: 3.1 O: 0.5 S: 5.5 N: 1.9 Ash: 0.3 Moisture: 6.5 18% excess oxygen is used.	Petroleum coke was used in kiln and calciner [wt%]: C: 85.5 H: 3.5 O: 1.8 S: 5.3 N: 1.8 Ash: 0.3 Moisture: 1.8 But, sulphur content in petcoke for calciner was changed so as to have up to 1% sulfidation rate in the Ca-looping process. Coal is used in the pre-calciner. <u>In the pre-calciner [wt%]:</u> C: 64.5 H: 4.5 O: 7.2 S: 0.9 N: 1.4 Ash: 12.0 Moisture: 9.5 10% excess oxygen is used.	In the <u>power plant</u> , the coal composition [wt%]: C: 61.6 H: 4.9 O: 15.5 N: 1.2 Ash: 6.7 Moisture: 10.1 No information was given for fuel compositions used in the kiln and calciner.
Carbonator	No carbonator in this system			
<i>Operating temperature</i>	-	650°C	650°C	650°C
<i>Pressure</i>	-	1.0 atm	1.0 atm	1.0 atm
<i>F₀/F_{CO2}</i>	-	4.5	0.2 – 5.8	A purge of 3.2% of the total solid inventory

F_{CaO}/F_{CO_2} W_s u_0 Reactor height Ca conversion Capture efficiency in the carbonator Net CO ₂ avoided efficiency Gas pressure drop Model used	- - - - 33%, it becomes 38% if CO ₂ emission by extra electricity is excluded. - -	- - - CaO conversion: 30 % - 99% -	1.9 – 5.5 Ws was set so as to have 0.1 bar ΔP along the carbonator. 6.0 m/s 10.0 m Approx. 30 % CaO conversion 90% 92- 99% 0.1 bar Carbonator modelling (Romano, 2012)	is assumed. 4 (fixed) - - - 90% 95.3% - There is no a reactor model implemented.
Calciner Operating temperature Calcination efficiency O ₂ content in oxidant stream	937 °C 100 % calcination Air used	950 °C 100 % calcination 25 vol% O ₂ (75 vol% CO ₂ and H ₂ O)	930 °C 100 % calcination 95 % O ₂ without CO ₂ dilution	950 °C 100 % calcination -
Steam cycle	A sub-critical steam cycle was chosen. (120 bar/520 °C/520 °C) No steam bleeds are performed.	Assumed that the lower temperature limit for energy recovery is 150 °C. The net thermal efficiency of 33% is estimated for steam cycle.	Estimated as an enthalpy generated when cooled down to 150 °C. The gross steam turbine efficiency of 46% was assumed.	180 bar/50 bar 600 °C/600 °C A pinch analysis has been conducted to recover maximum amount of surplus energy.
Air separation unit Electricity consumption O ₂ purity	- -	160 kWh/ton _{O₂} -	200 kWh/ton _{O₂} 95 vol % O ₂	220 kWh/ton _{O₂} -
CO₂ compression and purification Final CO ₂ pressure Final CO ₂ purity Compression train (Compressor efficiency) Overall specific consumption	100 bar > 95 vol % CO ₂ 5 turbo compressors + pump (75 % isentropic efficiency) -	- - - - 100 kWh/ton CO ₂	150 bar > 95 vol % CO ₂ 4 turbo compressors + pump (75 % isentropic efficiency) 120 kWh/ton CO ₂	- - - - -
Results				

<i>Total power demand (Cement plant + CO₂ compressor + Air separation unit + Auxiliaries)</i>	-	37.0 MWe	36.0 – 42.0 MWe	<p>The total thermal energy consumption of reference case (power + cement plants) increases 6.7% for the integrated system (power + cement + Ca-looping plants)</p> <p>The thermal energy requirement in the cement plant decreases by 39.5% since purge CaO can be fed to kiln without calcination.</p>
<i>Power production by steam cycle</i>	31.6 MWe	41.0 MWe	33.0 – 71.0 MWe	
<i>Energy demand of the base cement plant</i>	3.0 GJ/ton cement	2.9 GJ/ton cement	3.2 GJ/ton clinker	
<i>Energy demand of the base cement plant + Ca-looping process</i>	6.1 GJ/ton cement	5.5 GJ/ton cement	5.3 – 5.7 GJ/ton clinker	
<i>CO₂ avoided cost</i>	11.6 \$/t CO ₂	23.0 \$/t CO ₂	30.0 €/t CO ₂	

3.1 Guidelines for future works

Modelling of CaL process for CO₂ capture in cement plants has many similarities with the post-combustion capture from power plant flue gases case. Therefore, the suggestions described in section 1.2.1 can be extended to this case for both CaL reactors modeling and process simulation. An additional issue should however be considered for cement plants, related to the limited variability of the composition of the final clinker, which may limit the maximum amount of CaL purge to be used in the plant if too rich of CaSO₄ and ash.

3.2 References

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